

Ion-exchange Properties of 2,4-Dihydroxypropiophenone-Urea-Formaldehyde Copolymers

GAJENDRA C. PATEL and MOHANBHAI M. PATEL*

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

Manuscript received 9 August 1989, revised 1 February 1991, accepted 20 March 1991

Copolymers have been prepared by the condensation of 2,4-dihydroxypropiophenone urea and formaldehyde in the presence of 2M H₂SO₄ and 2M HCl as catalyst with varied molar ratios of reacting monomers, and characterised by ir spectra, elemental analyses, TGA, molecular weight determination and viscosity measurements. Chelation ion-exchange properties have been studied employing the batch equilibration method. The copolymer showed a higher selectivity for UO₂^{II} and Fe^{III} ions than Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} ions.

THE synthesis, characterisation and ion-exchange properties of 2,4-dihydroxypropiophenone-formaldehyde (2,4-DPP-F) copolymers have been reported¹. The present paper reports the synthesis, characterisation and ion-exchange properties of 2,4-dihydroxypropiophenone-urea-formaldehyde (2,4-DPP-U-F) polymers.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. 2,4-Dihydroxypropiophenone was prepared by the reported method². DMF was used after distillation.

Preparation of copolymers: A mixture of 2,4-DPP (16.6 g, 0.1 mol), 37% formaldehyde (16.2 ml, 0.2 mol) and 2M HCl (50.0 ml) was refluxed with stirring at 60° in an oil-bath and to which urea (6.0 g, 0.1 mol in 5 ml H₂O) was added dropwise and finally the reaction mixture was refluxed at 110° for 5 h. The solid yellow coloured product obtained was washed with large amount of boiling water followed by acetone to remove unreacted 2,4-DPP and urea. The copolymer was purified³ and finely ground (300 mesh). It was found soluble in DMF and pyridine and insoluble in common organic solvents. Other copolymer samples were prepared using different molar ratios of 2,4-DPP and catalyst (Table 1).

Elemental analyses, determination of $\bar{M}_n$, viscosity, ir spectra and thermogravimetric analyses were carried out as described earlier¹. The batch equilibrium method⁴ was adopted for studying the ion-exchange properties.

Results and Discussion

The probable structure of copolymers has been determined on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data. The copolymers do not melt upto 250°. The number average molecular weights ($\bar{M}_n$) of all the copolymer samples were determined by non-aqueous conductometric titration in pyridine using sodium methoxide in pyridine as titrant¹ and $\bar{M}_n$ values were calculated following a prescribed methods^{5,6}; $\bar{M}_n$ was also determined by vapour pressure osmometry in DMF at 71°. The values obtained by both methods are in good agreement. The copolymer sample obtained using equimolar proportion of the reactants showed comparatively higher molecular weight.

The viscosity measurements were carried out in DMF at 35° and plots of reduced viscosity vs concentration were made for each set of data. The intrinsic viscosity [η] was determined from the corresponding linear plots (Table 1). As expected, the

TABLE I—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COPOLYMERS

Compd.	Reactants			2M HCl ml	2M H ₂ SO ₄ ml	Yield %	Mol. weight		[η] × 10 ³ dl g ⁻¹
	2,4-DPP mol	Urea mol	Formaldehyde mol				VPO	Conductometric titration	
2,4-DPPUF-1	0.050	0.050	0.100	50.0	—	58.0	886	925	5.56
2,4-DPPUF-2	0.075	0.050	0.125	63.0	—	69.0	1 509	1 576	4.83
2,4-DPPUF-3	0.050	0.025	0.075	37.5	—	62.0	972	1 046	6.18
2,4-DPPUF-4	0.062	0.025	0.087	44.0	—	48.0	693	731	6.07
2,4-DPPUF-5	0.050	0.050	0.100	—	50.0	60.0	869	956	5.18
2,4-DPPUF-6	0.075	0.050	0.125	—	63.0	55.0	906	984	5.48
2,4-DPPUF-7	0.050	0.025	0.075	—	37.5	42.0	756	770	4.72
2,4-DPPUF-8	0.062	0.025	0.087	—	44.0	54.0	1 002	1 064	4.72

copolymers having higher M_n have higher values of $[\eta]$.

All the copolymers gave similar ir spectra. The reaction of urea and formaldehyde with 2,4-DPP in the presence of acid catalyst is an electrophilic substitution on the benzene ring.

A broad ir band appearing at 3 100–3 600 cm^{-1} is due to OH stretching vibration⁷. The strong $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band around 1 640 cm^{-1} and a weak ν_{OH} band around 2 740 cm^{-1} indicate an intramolecular H-bond⁸. The vibrational bands at 2 890 and 735 cm^{-1} suggest the presence of methylene bridges⁹. The phenolic OH in-plane bending is observed at 1 280 cm^{-1} . Bands at 1 045–1 240 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–H in-plane bending¹⁰. On the basis of the nature and reactive positions of the monomers, elemental analyses, molecular weights, ir spectra and taking into consideration the linear structure of other substituted phenol-formaldehyde copolymers¹¹ and linear branched nature of urea-formaldehyde copolymers¹², the structures proposed for the copolymers may be of two types : linearly branched structure (1) which may sparsely cross-linked through N-atom of urea unit and linear structure (2). Thus, the distribution of monomer units along the copolymer chain would be random.

All the copolymers undergo thermal degradation in single step and showed lower rate of decomposition in the beginning. Decomposition is completed at 550° where 70–95% weight-loss is observed.

Ion-exchange properties : The results of the batch equilibrium study carried out with copolymer sample 2,4-DPP-UF-2 reveal that the amount of Cu^{II} , UO_2^{II} and Fe^{III} ions taken up by copolymer sample increases with increasing concentration of ClO_4^- , NO_3^- and Cl^- and decreases with increasing concentration of SO_4^{2-} , whereas uptake of Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} ions by the copolymer increases with decreasing concentration of ClO_4^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} . A

probable explanation is the stability constants of complexes formed by Fe^{III} , UO_2^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with these ligands^{13,14}. Sulphate might form strong complexes, while perchlorate, nitrate and chloride form weak complexes with Cu^{II} , UO_2^{II} and Fe^{III} ions. Whereas Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} ions might form strong complexes with ClO_4^- , Cl^- and NO_3^- and hence their metal uptake increases with the decreasing concentration of electrolyte. This type of trend has also been observed by other investigation^{1,3,4,13}.

The rate of metal adsorption of 2,4-DPP-UF-2 was determined to evaluate the shortest period of time for which equilibration could be carried out while operating as close to equilibrium conditions as possible. The results indicate that Fe^{III} and UO_2^{II} ions required slightly more than 3 h for the establishment of the equilibrium, whereas Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} ions required 6 h. In case of UO_2^{II} and Fe^{III} ions more than 55% equilibrium was established in the first hour. The rate of metal ion uptake follows the order : Fe^{III} , UO_2^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} , Zn^{II} .

The effect of pH on the amount of metal ion distributed between the two phases was carried out only upto pH 6 in order to prevent hydrolysis of the metal ions at a higher pH. In case of Fe^{III} and UO_2^{II} the highest value of working pH was 2.5. UO_2^{II} ion is taken up more selectively than any other metal ion under study. The lower distribution ratio of Fe^{III} than UO_2^{II} may be attributed to steric hindrance imposed by polymer matrix which inhibits the completion of the Fe^{III} d^5 sp^3 hybrid with 3 units of 2,4-DPP-UF copolymer as opposed to the formation of the chelate of Fe^{III} with three units of 2,4-DPP monomer. UO_2^{II} needs only 2 units of 2,4-DPP-UF copolymer for completion of its coordination requirement which is easily accomplished¹³. Co^{II} and Zn^{II} have low distribution ratio in the pH range 4–6. This can be attributed to the low stability constant, i.e. weak ligand stabilisation energy of the metal complexes^{15,16}. The observed order of distribution ratios of divalent metal ions measured in the pH range 3–6 was found to be : UO_2^{II} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} .

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (G.C.P.) is thankful of Gujarat Government for awarding a research fellowship.

References

1. B. K. PATEL and M. M. PATEL, *Angew. Makromol. Chem.*, 1989, **165** 47.
2. C. M. BREWSTER and J. C. HARRIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 4866.
3. K. D. PATEL and M. M. PATEL, *Indian J. Technol.*, 1989, **27**, 541.
4. B. S. PATEL and S R PATEL, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1979, **180**, 1159.
5. S. K. CHATTERJEE, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A*, 1970, **8** 1299.
6. S. K. CHATTERJEE and V. S. AGRAWAL, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A*, 1971, **9**, 3225.

PATEL & PATEL : ION-EXCHANGE PROPERTIES OF 2,4-DIHYDROXYPROPIOPHENONE-UREA *etc.*

7. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, R. PAL and R. L. GOEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 33.
8. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Nankodo, Japan, 1964, pp. 20, 30, 50.
9. B. D. GUPTA and W. V. MALIK, *J. Less-Common Met.*, 1969, **17**, 277.
10. J. R. DYER, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", 2nd. ed., Prentice-Hall of India, New Delhi, pp. 33-37.
11. R. C. DEGRISO, L. G. DONARUMA and E. A. TOMIC, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 845.
12. I. Y. SLONIM, S. G. ALEKSEVA and B. M. ARSHAVA, *Vysokomol. Soedin.*, 1977, **19(3)**, 163 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **86**, 172235).
13. A. BJERRUM, G. SCHWABZENBACH and L. G. SILLEN, "Stability Constant of Complex Molecules", The Chemical Society, London, 1958, Vol. 1, p. 83.
14. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Willey-Interscience, New York, 1952, p. 594.
15. S. L. DAVADOV and N. A. PLATE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **16**, 195.
16. H. IRVING and F. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **56**, 271.